

An Exploration of Cloud-based Technologies for Enhancing Emergency Management Capabilities in New Zealand Natural Emergencies

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ABSTRACT

In response to a lack of existing theory explaining the possible association between cloud-based technology (C-BT) deployment and emergency management, this paper explores the perceived value C-BT can provide within the emergency management sector, with a specific focus on natural disasters. The research used multiple data sources including semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and observations to achieve triangulation in findings. The adoption of grounded theory analysis has resulted in the identification of key elements influencing perception of C-BT deployment in natural disasters. Findings indicate that organizational readiness, coordination, individual perception, individual readiness, C-BT characteristics, and non C-BT redundancy constitute the key dimensional elements influencing the perceived C-BT usage in natural disasters. The findings serve as a knowledge base for emergency professionals in both New Zealand and other countries that are also coping with frequent natural disasters to enhance their organisational and individual readiness in C-BT usage in natural disasters, leading to more effective emergency management performance.

Keywords: cloud-based technology, usage perception, preparedness, response

INTRODUCTION

This unpredictability of natural disasters means it is challenging for emergency managers to make appropriate emergency management decisions even with current technologies. New Zealand presents an interesting case, as it is a country that is frequently affected by earthquakes and floods, such as Kaikoura magnitude 7.8 earthquake in South Island 2016 and severe flooding in Northland in April 2017. Thus, special attention needs to be paid on this country with relatively high frequency of disasters. Thus, this paper explores the perceived value of cloud-based technology (C-BT) for enhancing emergency management capabilities in New Zealand natural events.

C-BTs have the great potential to provide an effective and efficient way in information sharing, data backup and resource accessibility in dealing with emergency management. It has been proved to show its successful usage in several recent natural disasters. For example, the cloud geographic information system helped agencies quickly respond during the 2010 Brisbane floods (Yu et al., 2013); web-based volunteer geographic information was used to disseminate the current situation of the hazard and evacuation area in the immediate aftermath of 2011 Christchurch earthquake (Roche et al., 2013); and cloud-based data was used to back up thousands of health records following the 2011 Great Eastern Japan Earthquake (Nagata et al., 2013).

Despite the recognition of the significance of C-BT in emergency management, vast majority of the prior literature explores the technical designs of cloud-based emergency response systems (Eckle et al., 2016; Negahban & Nourjou, 2016). Little attention has been paid to an investigation of how C-BT deployment are perceived by emergency service organizations in the specific emergency roles of preparedness and response of natural disasters. The primary reason for focusing on these two key stages is due to the fact that the real-time attribute of a technology is especially important in preparation for and response to unexpected natural disasters in which it emphasises the technology's ability in gathering and disseminating reliable and large quantity of information as quickly as possible to help in decision-making. This paper contributes to the

small but growing literature that focuses on the technology usage in emergency management, which is quantitative and survey based (Hu & Kapucu, 2014; Kapucu, Garayev, & Wang, 2013; Rahm & Reddick, 2013). This paper is qualitative and has a strong focus on the social perspective that investigate the emergency professionals' perceptions of C-BT usage in emergency management context.

The remainder of the paper is structure as follows: first, it presents a discussion C-BT benefits in emergency management. This is followed by the method of data collection and analysis. Next the key findings are presented, framed by a multi-dimensional model. The paper ends with a brief conclusion.

C-BT BENEFITS FOR EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

Decentralisation

With decentralization, the data back-up is automatically conducted across different data centers around the world. Thus it is less possible to loss the data, especially in the natural disasters. It is argued that data availability, backups and redundancy are important considerations when considering emergency management software due to the real possibility of losing access to computers and data centers (Li et al., 2013). For example, the Great East Japan earthquake in 2011 resulted in loss of important data in terms of birth and residents' records (Sakurai & Kokuryo, 2013). The lesson of failure motivated the municipal government to consider cloud computing technologies into consideration because it enables the data and applications to be stored in the network rather than local servers.

Scalability

C-BT provides scalable services to the users so that they can flexibly use any cloud-based services with peak or sudden decrease in demand. For example, when there is a high demand in analysing large data set of geospatial and mapping information, cloud-GIS can provide better support on computing requirements to help researchers to conduct natural hazard analysis, such as analysing an earthquake (Hofer, 2015), or tsunami (Theilen-Willige & Wenzel, 2012). As a result, this type of knowledge can be delivered to emergency planners in a timely manner. Cloud services thus provide highly scalable services on applications that the user wants to use in natural disasters.

Ubiquitous Access

Generally, it is always accessible to cloud-based services at any place and any time. Although unexpected situations such as power outage or disconnections might happen especially during natural disasters. As long as there is generators or satellites, it is still accessible to cloud services. During natural disasters, internet connection might be disrupted. However, people who are not in the affected area could still use the functions of the social network to disperse or get emergency information from the emergency service organisations.

Economy of Scale

Cloud computing can help emergency service organisations to save costs if they have budget constraints. It is because it is more affordable for them to rent IT services compared to making heavy investments in those IT infrastructures, thus allowing them to focus more on their core competencies. For example, some open cloud GIS platform has drawn increasing attention by the public users. Some well-known examples include OpenStreetMap, Ushahidi, and RinkWatch, which encourages anyone in the public or emergency agencies to share relevant event information on the website through usable ways such as Short Message Service (SMS), e-mail, Facebook or Twitter (Roche et al., 2013). In the case of 2010 severe flooding in Australia, the Brisbane City Council established a crowd-sourced map on the Ushahidi platform through making a call for volunteers to help (Awange & Kiema, 2013).

Reduced Maintenance Effort

Cloud services help emergency services organisations to pay less effort on IT which is not their core business. With the accessible and scalable services, they can focus more on the use of the data for decision making. For example, social media platforms can be used to share information to enhance the readiness of the public such as helping individuals, communities and agencies to share emergency plans and establish emergency networks (Merchant et al., 2011). Therefore, emergency services organisations can take advantages of many different sources of open free platforms that do not require high level of maintenance effort in dealing with natural disasters.

METHOD

The is a qualitative case study, being conducted within the organisation in the emergency service sector in New Zealand in which the C-BT plays an important role when dealing with natural disasters. The collected data in this paper involve face-to-face semi-structured interviews with five participants, one focus group comprising four members, and two non-participating exercise observations, including large scale earthquake and tsunami exercises, each lasting approximately eight hours. The participants consisted of professionals working at both managerial and operational levels in the emergency service organisation. Therefore, the involvement of participants from different levels in the organisation and the multiple sources of data allow for multiple perspectives and enhanced data source triangulation. Data were analysed through grounded theory analysis. However, this is not a pure grounded theory (GT) approach whereby it uses the relevant aspects of GT in analysing the data, following Strauss and Corbin's (1990) three stage coding process. Totally, 296 incidents were grouped into 98 concepts and then were categorized into 13 more abstracted categories and six core categories.

FINDINGS

The research proposes six dimensions of C-BT deployment factors, consisting of organizational readiness, coordination, individual perception, individual readiness, C-BT characteristics and non C-BT redundancy (See Figure 1). Findings indicate various organisational, individual, and technological elements that influence the successful deployment of C-BT in natural disasters. The application of information technologies represents a critical process during the emergency management operation. The core C-BT the organisation uses in the response stage is a private cloud. The C-BT usage in the preparedness is limited, mainly involving the data storage. C-BT deployment refers to the emergency professionals' willingness to utilise C-BTs in the natural events.

The dimension of organisation readiness consists of usage frequency, usage, preparedness, capacity, and training. The coordination is associated with the interagency coordination. The individual perception is comprised of perceived advantages, perceived disadvantages, and enhancement expectation. The individual readiness involves human factor and knowledge. The C-BT characteristics is associated with usefulness and deployment model type. The non C-BT redundancy relates to offline redundancy, which refers to paper forms and alternative ways for communication, such as satellite to support reconnection of the cloud service if power outages or disconnections happen.

Results show that organisational readiness and individual perceptions have stronger impacts on emergency professionals' perception of C-BT deployment in natural events. It is because most of the elements emerge from these two core categories and have great influence on the emergency professionals' perceptions of C-BT deployment in natural disasters. Totally, 53 out of 98 concepts were emerged under these two categories.

Fig. 1. Dimensional elements influencing C-BT deployment in natural disasters

Specifically, the findings show that:

- 1) In terms of organisational readiness greater frequency of C-BT usage, consistent C-BT usage readiness at both government and local level, the greater capacity, as well as the frequent and consistent training increases the emergency professional's positive perceptions in C-BT deployment in natural disasters. In particular, the Usage frequency has greater impact in the response stage and the training has greater impact in the preparedness stage.
- 2) In respect of coordination, the greater inter-agency coordination increases the emergency professionals' positive perceptions in C-BT deployment in natural disasters especially in the preparedness stage for a smoother cooperation operation in the response stage.
- 3) In terms of individual perception, the greater perceived advantages (e.g., accessibility, data certainty, cost-saving on external cloud, flexibility on mobile devices), the less perceived disadvantages (e.g., security, privacy, compatibility, complexity, cost on self-maintenance), and the greater enhancement expectation satisfaction result in emergency professionals' more positive perceptions in C-BT deployment in natural disasters.
- 4) With regard to individual readiness, the greater willingness to change, confidence in system usage and stronger C-BT knowledge increases the emergency professionals' positive perceptions on C-BT deployment in natural disasters.
- 5) In association with C-BT characteristics, the greater usefulness and mixed usage C-BT deployment model type has a strong effect on emergency professionals' positive perception of C-BT deployment in natural disasters.
- 6) The greater offline redundancy increases the emergency professionals' C-BT deployment in the response stage of natural events. This is because with paper-based redundancy (e.g. forms and contact lists) and communication redundancy (e.g. satellite), they would have more confidence in using C-BT even when unexpected situations such as power outages or disconnections happen.

CONCLUSION

This research aims to investigate the New Zealand emergency service professionals' perceptions regarding C-BT usage in natural events. Through reviewing the current research in this area, there is a lack of study discovering the C-BT usage perception from the organisational perspective. Thus, the paper contributes to the body of knowledge in the field of emergency management by through offering in-depth understanding about the phenomenon that contributes to the theoretical model development about the factors influencing emergency professionals' perceptions in C-BT deployment in natural events. Thirteen main propositions have been formulated that suggest the influences of the perceived C-BT usage relate to the organisational readiness, individual readiness, technology characteristics and non-C-BT redundancy. Organisational readiness and individual perception has the stronger effect on perceived C-BT deployment in natural events. From a practical viewpoint, the findings can serve as a knowledge base for the emergency professionals in both New Zealand and other countries that are also coping with frequent natural disasters to enhance their organisational and individual readiness in C-BT usage in natural events, leading to more effective emergency management performance.

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